

OF SCIENTIFIC TEMPER AND COVID-19 IN CONTEMPORARY INDIA

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Abstract

This paper intends to explain the need for and importance of a thriving scientific ecosystem in India to deal with the crisis of a global magnitude like Covid 19. In the wake of the abrupt outbreak of this pandemic, it has been found that the common masses in different parts of India have resorted to the use of all kinds of superstitious and unscientific remedies to get rid of this virus. The social media was also replete with ample dogmatic and pseudo-scientific solutions to contain Covid 19. This kind of irrational and unscientific response on the part of the common people revealed the glaring deficiency of scientific temper even in this digital age after more than seventy years of independence. This qualitative research is carried out to recognize how the absence of a scientific temperament among the common masses posed a challenge to the society and the government in India at large to fight Covid 19. In view of this, the creation of a scientific ecosystem in India has become so important today as never before when New Delhi is aspiring to become a global power. Thus, there is an inevitable necessity to inculcate the much-needed scientific temper among the masses in India today. This could be achieved only by an active collaboration of all the stakeholders- the civil society, the scientific community, the Non-Governmental Organizations, and the government.

Keywords: Pseudoscience, Superstitions, Civil Society. Pandemic, Public Health.

Introduction

As the scourge of Covid-19 pandemic kept on wreaking havoc in India like many other countries around the world, it has been found that many Indians living in cities and villages resorted to the use of orthodox and superstitious practices to get rid of the virus. Reports came pouring in almost daily in both print as well as the electronic media as to how the people are engaged in practicing all kinds of pseudoscience to ward off the Corona virus. In several districts of Uttar Pradesh, people were busy in holding '*bhajans*' (religious hymns), special *pujas*(worship) and *havans* (a ritual by fire for common welfare) at temples to avoid the Covid infection ('Uttar Pradesh Villagers Turn to Gods, Superstitions as Covid-19 Wreaks Havoc', n.d.). In Ballari, a village in North Karnataka, the villagers kept a mixture of cooked rice and the blood of rooster along village borders to ward off the evil spirits ('Age Old Beliefs Spring up in North Karnataka to Ward off Corona, Rationalists Take a Dig', n.d.).

These are only few of the numerous incidents of superstitious practices resorted to by the people to fight the Covid-19 pandemic in the deeply diverse society of India. If anything, these incidents indicate the reality that even in this digital age, a large section of the Indian populace still cling to the use of religious, dogmatic, and unscientific practices to deal with any major health emergencies. This speaks volumes about the current state of the much needed 'Scientific temper' about which the Indian leaders like Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru talked so vociferously in the initial years of independence to lay a strong foundation for India's future nationhood. But unfortunately, even after more than seven decades of India's independence and even in this age of internet, the common masses in India and in some cases even the educated people are also engaged in such dogmatic and obscurantist practices to deal with the eventualities of life. It reveals how our so-called digital age contradicts and indeed smacks the real-life encounters in dealing with the impending crises around us.

Like all other countries in the world, the government in India started taking a host of preventive and proactive steps on a war-footing to contain Covid-19 by issuing necessary advisories to the people in this regard. The challenge was nevertheless insurmountable keeping in view the poor public health infrastructure of India. The severity of the threat can be gauged from the fact that the number of Covid infected people jumped from 1 lakh to 1.5 lakh within a week ('COVID19 India News Live Updates 27 May 2020: Coronavirus Cases Cross 1.5 Lakh - Grainmart News', n.d.). The Union Ministry of Health and Family Welfare made repeated appeals to the people to bring appropriate behavioural

changes to deal with the pandemic. Keeping in view the novelty of the virus and the absence of vaccines to deal with it, the only option left for the government was to empower the citizens with the right information in the form of advisories. These advisories were being updated from time to time to ensure their efficacy depending upon the changing nature and effects of the virus.

Objectives

This study has been undertaken with the following objectives in mind:

1. To gain a conceptual understanding of 'Scientific Temper' in India.
2. To understand the importance and development of 'Scientific temper' in the diversified social structure of India.
3. To unearth some of the superstitious practices used by the people to deal with Covid 19.
4. To understand the challenges faced by the society and the government in India to effectively contain the Covid 19 pandemic.
5. To come out with practicable and socially useful suggestions and recommendations to prevent a recurrence of the same.

Review of Literature

The concept of scientific temper is not something new to India. Several thousands of years ago, thinkers and philosophers subscribing to different materialist traditions like the Samkhyas, the Charvakas, the Jains and the Buddhists emphasized the importance of questioning the unverified phenomena both in moral as well as natural universe ('(PDF) Quest for Scientific Temper', n.d.). Raja Rammohan Roy, one of the greatest social reformers of modern India appealed to his countrymen to develop a rational and scientific outlook to age old traditions and belief systems (Narlikar 2003). Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru in his much acclaimed book *The Discovery of India* (Nehru 1946) called for the development of scientific temper in India. In his capacity as the Prime Minister of India, he urged both the common people as well as the scientists to create a scientifically minded society to ensure national progress. The Scientific Policy Resolution ('Science Technology and Innovation (STI) Policies in India: A Flashback - IndiaBioscience', n.d.) passed by the Government of India in both the Houses of Parliament also affirmed the faith of India's political leadership on the important role of science and technology in national development.

Following Nehru's death, the Government of India revised and re-formulated its efforts to inculcate scientific temper in the citizens by making it a fundamental duty. The Indian government passed the forty-second amendment Act in 1976 and inserted a clause that says that it shall be the duty of every citizen of India 'To develop the scientific temper, humanism and a spirit of inquiry and reform' (Shukla 1988). It was believed that by making the development of scientific temperament a fundamental duty under the constitution, the common masses would imbibe the habit of having a scientific and rational outlook to life. But unfortunately, this did not happen. It is unfortunate that despite the enormous strides India has made in science and technology today, Nehru's vision of scientific temper permeating at all levels of Indian society remains a dream.

To understand and explain the rationale, impact and ramifications of the use of pseudoscientific methods to treat Covid-19, this researcher has gone through several reported news items on print, electronic as well as the social media. In view of the huge number of such reported cases, only a few of such reported incidents are discussed here keeping in view the nature, scope, and objectives of this paper.

Research Methodology

This study mostly used the secondary data in collecting, explaining, and analyzing the unscientific and irrational response of the common masses in India to Covid-19. Information is being collected from a wide array of sources like newspapers, websites, social media as well as academic sources like books and research papers from journals indexed in Scopus and Web of Science. Information gathered from these diverse sources are used to explain the conceptual formulations of 'scientific temper' in Indian context with the help of descriptive and historical methods. Analytical method has been taken recourse

to explain and understand the impact of the use of pseudo-scientific methods on the individual and society in the backdrop of the frequent appeals made by the scientific community and the Indian government to show a rational and scientific attitude to deal with this pandemic.

Results and Discussion

To common people, the concept of ‘Scientific temper’ seems to be the reserve of the scientific community- people who actively pursue a carrier in scientific research and development to comprehend and unravel the natural phenomena. It is the general belief of the masses that the concept of ‘Scientific temper’ is something far from reality and thus of no use to them. The reality is that scientific temperament implies a rational and scientific attitude to life itself. It’s a way of thinking. It propels us not to accept anything as final or true unless it passes the test of scientific enquiry. A man with scientific temper never accepts anything as final without a rational enquiry or questioning it using his reasoning power. This is not something altogether new to human society. Centuries ago, the famous Greek philosopher Socrates said that ‘the unexamined life is not worth living’. So, it is very important for us to use our highly developed mental faculty to raise the level of our existence.

Scientific temper is essential to the development of the individual as well as a nation. It is necessary for the citizens of a nation to inculcate the quality of scientific temper to ensure the overall progress of the nation in social, economic, and political fields. A nation believing in giving religious, unscientific, and dogmatic explanation to justify human and natural phenomenon could not make much progress. It is because of this that the first Prime Minister of India, Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru so emphatically sought to imbibe scientific temper among the people of India in the initial years of India’s nationhood. Nehru underlined the inevitability of scientific attitude to strengthen democracy and secularism in India. So, he wanted that the layman must be made to understand that the scientific method is the only way to know the truth. For he knew that India could not make much progress on social and political fronts without leaving her age-old superstitions and dogmatic beliefs.

But unfortunately, even after the passing of more than seventy years of independence, the common masses and even the educated ones still demonstrate a strong inclination towards superstitious beliefs and dogmas. Strangely enough, while we never hesitate to embrace the benefits of science to enhance the quality of our lives, we do rarely give lip service to the use of scientific method to unfold the truth and arrive at a reasonable explanation of the happenings around us. The basic stumbling block in the creation of a scientific climate in India ‘is the uncritical acceptance of the dictates of religion, dogma, faith, customs, convention and tradition’ (Bhargava, P M Acharya and Bhushan B 2008). Unfortunately, this phenomenon has been amply demonstrated during the Covid-19 pandemic.

The call for unity and resolve to fight Corona virus given by Prime Minister Narendra Modi on 22nd March 2020 had been misinterpreted and miscommunicated by the vested interest groups including the highly educated ones. Pranksters and even the so called digitally literate ones used the social media to spread misinformation by giving unverified and misleading information. Widespread digitization and penetration of internet usage following the Government of India’s Digital Initiative greatly popularized the use of social media platforms among the common masses. According to a report recently published by the Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI) and Kantar, the number of internet users in India is supposed to exceed 900 million by 2025. The report says that both urban and rural users spend an average of 90 minutes daily in accessing the internet (‘Internet Users in India 2025: India to Exceed 900 Mn Internet Users by 2025 | News - Business Standard’, n.d.). This growing digitization has made social media vulnerable to misuse by the vested interest groups to fulfill their nefarious designs.

As Indians came out in huge numbers on their balconies and lawns banging utensils, clapping, and ringing bells in response to Prime Minister Modi’s call for ‘Janata Curfew’ to boost the morale of the essential service workers, a fake WhatsApp message was circulating in social media claiming that the sound was making Corona virus retreat. The message reads, NASA satellite videos LIVE telecast have shown that the Corona virus is retreating in India because of the clapping call given by PM Modi. (‘Fact Check: NASA Satellite Didn’t Show Coronavirus Retreat in India Due To 5PM Clapping’, n.d.). This was a fake and misleading information because there was neither the evidence of NASA SD

13 wave detector nor a biosatellite is meant for tracking developments or spread of a virus. So, to contain the spread of this kind of misinformation the government immediately issued directives to different social media companies like YouTube, Facebook, TikTok, ShareChat and Twitter. These companies were urged to immediately initiate awareness campaigns and take away all misinformed and incriminating materials from their social media platforms.

Many private organisations came forward to support the government to counter the rapidly growing misinformation and fake news. An online platform by the name of Indian Scientists' Response to COVID-19 (ISRC) played an important role to counter the rapidly spreading popular hoaxes relating to the pandemic ('After "COVID Katha" & "Break the Fake Toons", ARMT Shows the Way for Students with "MOTIVATION"', n.d.). This online platform consisting of more than 500 scientists from over 50 research and scientific institutes played the role of hoax-busters by educating the people neither to believe in superstitions nor engage in other unscientific practices.

The organisation by the name of Dr. Anamika Ray Memorial Trust (ARMT) also undertook an awareness campaign to counter the mischiefs and fake news being deliberately spread by the vested interest groups to foil the efforts of the government to contain the pandemic. Taking inspiration from the World Health Organisation's warning that 'Infodemic' is much deadlier than the 'pandemic', the ARMT through its campaigns tried to show how the common people act irrationally by coming under the influence of the 'Infodemic' ('Coronavirus: Pandemic, Infodemic: 2 Cartoon Characters Battling Fake News In Assam', n.d.). This awareness campaign greatly helped to sensitize the common people regarding the dangers of misinformation, misbeliefs, and superstitions to public health in the country.

Conclusion

It is indeed a great challenge to bring quick behavioural changes in the diversified social structure of India to check the spread of Corona virus. Nevertheless, the Prime Minister and the government at large have made repeated appeals to the people to maintain social distancing, create social awareness and appreciate the works done by the COVID warriors. But these messages were misinterpreted and misrepresented in a way that gave rise to belief in superstition and spread of conspiracy theories in different social media platforms. In view of this, the government emphasised on the need to educate the people on the importance of social distancing to check the spread of this deadly virus ('Counter Misinformation, Superstition on Coronavirus: PM to Social Workers - The Economic Times', n.d.). Therefore, all the stakeholders- the print and the electronic media, the Non-Governmental Organisations and the government at local, state and national levels need to act in a coordinated and systematic manner to inculcate scientific temper among the common masses. At the same time, the social media needs to be regulated as the absence of any gatekeeping mechanism, it falls prey to all kinds of regressive content which spread like wildfire. The government on its part also needs to encourage both the public and private sector organisations involved in healthcare, communication, and science to disseminate scientific temper and spirit of enquiry. The government needs to come out with new laws and regulations to check and prevent the practice of any kind of superstitious practices during this kind of health exigencies.

Thus, it is high time that the people of India must imbibe a cult of scientific temper and spirit of enquiry to ensure both individual as well as national progress. It is earnestly hoped that this pandemic shall strengthen our collective resolve to do away with all kinds of misbeliefs and superstitions responsible for letting us down all in these years.

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